

Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village, Gianyar

Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani¹, Ni Luh Putu Krisnawati², Ni Ketut Widhiarcani Matradewi³

^{1,2,3} Faculty of Humanities, Udayana University, Jalan Pulau Nias 13 Denpasar, Bali-Indonesia

ABSTRACT: This research entitled "Linguistics Landscape of Batu Bulan Village Area, Gianyar". This research was conducted with the aims at analyzing landscape dynamics in Batu Bulan village, Gianyar and also analyzing the language usage of the LL. The method applied for this research is a non-participatory observation method, using image capture technique, note-taking technique and literature study. The theory applied in this research is Linguistic Landscape (LL) from Landry and Bourhis (1997).

The research found that 421 outdoor signs of Linguistic Landscapes found in Batu Bulan village includes various classification, such as art galleries, banks and money exchange places, health services, hotels/accommodation, legal offices, supermarkets/minimarkets/cellphone shops, restaurants/cafes/dining places, spas, salons, studios, other services, non-commercial signs, street signs and names, temples, furniture, stone carvings and laundry. The language used in Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village can be found in the form of the usage of Balinese, Indonesian, English, a combination of English and others and universal symbols (traffic signs). The dominant use of language in the linguistic landscape is the use of Indonesian; there were found 254 units, followed by the use of English of 86 units, Balinese language of 45 units, the combination of English, Indonesian, Balinese and other usage is 27 units. The traffic signs are the fewest outdoor signs found in this village.

KEYWORDS: Linguistic Landscape, Outdoor signs, Batu Bulan, Gianyar.

INTRODUCTION

The term Linguistic Landscape is sub-part of Sociolinguistics which specializes in the study of street names, place names, advertisements, traffic signs, offices, information boards, shop signs and so on, as well as everything related to urban information viewed from a linguistic point of view. Landry and Bourhis (1997:23) state that the Linguistic Landscapes (LL) terminology refers to the visibility and salience of languages in public and commercial signs in a given territory or region. It is proposed that the linguistic landscape may serve important informational and symbolic functions as a marker of the relative power and status of the linguistic communities inhabiting the territory"

We can find LL in various forms in a city and the nature is universal. LL can not only be found in Indonesia, but also in other parts of the world. The exploration of Linguistic Landscape in Indonesia has been carried out by some linguists. There are ample of studies of LL in Indonesia such as by Syamsurijal (2023) concerning LL in Shopping Center in Makasar, Arneta Iftia Pramadhani et.al (2022) who explore LL in Malang City, Purnawati et.al (2022) explores Linguistic Landscape in heritage area of Gajah Mada Denpasar, Suta Paramarta (2022) discusses Virtual Linguistic Landscape (VLL) in government website of Bali Province, Puspani et.al (2021) concern with signposts in Nusa Penida island, Mulyawan (2017) finds out LL in tourism destination Kuta Bali and many others.

LL dynamics reflect the importance of language in a community. The language used in landscape dynamics is not only aimed at providing information, but can also reflect the power and status of language. The use of English in public places, billboards, traffic signs, offices, information boards, shop signs and so on, as well as every outdoor sign related to urban information becomes a phenomenon that needs to be identified and later mapped. Research of LL in Bali can be considered still small in number compare to other researches of LL that have been carried out outside the island. Therefore, this research tries to give additional information of LL in Bali. It tries to explore one of regencies of Bali, Gianyar regency; a regency which is well known for its art, artists, culture and features the most tourist destinations among other regencies. Put fold together, this research tries to reveal the LL dynamics in Batu Bulan village and also to analyze the language use in the dynamic LL of Batu Bulan.

METHOD

The data source of this research is all LL data in the area of Batu Bulan village. This village well-known among other villages in Gianyar Regency; it is known for its art and Barong dance performance. The method and technique of collecting data was done by taking several steps, they are: (1) Observing the area of research with other members of the group research before conducting field research to the locus of research, (2) Taking picture to all outdoor signs of Batu Bulan village, (3) Identifying all the captured images based on the language pattern and language use, (4) Classifying the landscape dynamics found into several categorizations and note the data into tables, (5) All the data were analyzed by theory of Linguistic Landscape by Landry and Burhois (1997)

The data was collected by observation method and apply image capture technique and documentation technique and also supported by literature study. The research is qualitative research and the analysis of the data is presented descriptively. The use of table in the following part applies as static descriptive to give information and elucidate the overview of the data.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Linguistic Landscape dynamic of Batu Bulan village

Table I. Linguistic Landscape Dynamics of Batu Bulan village

No	LL Classification	Outdoor signs
1	Art Gallery & Exhibition	16
2	Bank & Money Changer	22
3	Health Care Services	14
4	Hotel / Accommodation	11
5	Legal Office	16
6	School & Education	15
7	Supermarket, Minimarket, Shop, Phone shop	85
8	Restaurant / Cafe / Food Court	57
9	Spa, Salon, Studio	16
10	Other Services	65
11	Non- Commercial Sign	18
12	Traffic Sign & Street Names	53
13	Temple	14
14	Furniture	6
15	Stone Carving	5
16	Laundry	8
Total		421

As stated by Gorter and Cenoz, (2006:2), Linguistic Landscape concern with the form of written language in public spaces. Public spaces provide opportunity for society to interact and communicate not only verbally but also through writings. All the writings seen in public commonly deliver specific meaning and also messages. They can be featured as in commercial or non-commercial signs. To differentiate the signs, it represented in 'top-down' and 'bottom up' classification, Shohamy and Gorter (2009). Top-down terminology is intended for authorities, public bureaucracies, and covers public places, public announcements, and street names, while bottom-up terminology is intended for private parties, individual social actors, such as shop owners and private companies. For top-down feature usually there are certain concepts or procedures that need to be followed such as rules/instruction as it is instructed from the top (national level) to down (grass-root level). However, this must not be applied when it concerns with bottom-up LL classification. Majority the signs or outdoor signs will have no certain concept or procedures; they usually performed with various creative ideas, type of writings, colour and designs.

The above table show the findings of the dynamic of Linguistic Landscape in Batu Bulan village of Gianyar (Table 1). There is various LL classification found in this village; it shows the diversity and the healthy economic environment of the village. The LL dynamics can be seen in the various art gallery and exhibition, bank and money changer, health care services, hotel/accommodation,

legal offices, school and education, supermarket, minimarket, shop, phone shop, Restaurant / Cafe / Food Court, Spa, Salon, Studio, other services, non-commercial signs, traffic signs and street names, temple, furniture, stone carving and laundry.

The top-down signs found in school and education, traffic signs and street names and temple. There was found fifteen (15) outdoor signs of school and education LL classification, 53 outdoor signs of traffic signs and street names and fourteen (14) outdoor signs of temples. Meanwhile, the rest of the signs are considered as the bottom-up classification. The Supermarket, minimarket, shop and phone shop is the dominant LL classification found in this village. There are eighty-five (85) outdoor signs found for this classification. It represents how the economic cycle is healthy even though there might be perception of being capitalized by western ideology and affected by fast, modern lifestyle that has been penetrated in the society. The least LL classification found is the stone carving signs. There was found only five (5) outdoor signs of this classification. This happen due to the fact that Batu Bulan village is the neighbouring village of Singapadu; it is known as a village of stone carving.

Some examples of the outdoor signs found in this research are represented as follows:

Figure 1 -Village Sign

Figure 2 -Temple Sign

Figure 3- School

Figure 4- Tourism Sign

Figure 5 -Beauty salon

Figure 6- Marketing Sign

Figure 1-3 shows the example of top to down LL classification. They present village, temple and school signs. In Figure 1 we can see that the village sign is engraved in Indonesian and also figure 2 and 3. The difference among those top-down signs is that figure 2 features Balinese inscription under the national language. Meanwhile, figure 4-6 shows example of bottom-up classification. They are tourism, beauty salon and marketing signs. The tourism sign features its sign by using English; implicitly it is provided for foreigners not the locals. In figure 5 the outdoor sign of a beauty salon is presented in combination language, English and Indonesia. The title of the sign says “Laksmita Wedding”, however the other supporting explanation is provided in Indonesian. Figure 6 represents marketing sign which dominantly use English in the banner.

The language use in the LL of Batu Bulan village

This part concerns with the result of the research concerning the language use in the LL of Batu Bulan village. The finding shows that the type of language use are Balinese, Indonesian, English, Combination (English, Indonesia, Balinese and others) and also Universal symbols (traffic signs). The dominant language use in Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village is Indonesian. This presents the implementation of President Regulation number 63/2019. The regulation mandates the use of the Indonesian language that should be used dominantly in various aspects of written and verbal communication. The following usage applied is English, and the followed by Balinese, Combination languages and also universal symbols (traffic signs). The use of English found as the second language use in the linguistic landscape of Batu Bulan shows that some signs are dedicated for foreigners. The availability of the outdoor signs is expected able to communicate signs and information in the surrounding village. The findings are shown in the following table (table 2) and pie chart (figure 1)

Table II. Language use in Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan Gianyar

No	Language	Amount
1	Balinese	45
2	Indonesian	254
3	English	86
4	Combination (English + Indonesian+Bali+Others)	27
5	Universal symbols (Traffic Signs)	9
Total		421

Figure II. language use in Batu Bulan landscape

Figure 2 represents the percentage of the language use in Batu Bulan landscape in the form of the pie chart. It shows the dominant language use is Indonesian, represented in the blue colored pie chart. The least language use is the universal signs (traffic signs) featured in light blue colored pie chart. It was found only 9 outdoor signs or equal to 2 percents of the total outdoor signs found in this landscape.

There is various LL classification found in this village; it shows the diversity and the healthy economic environment of the village. The LL dynamics can be seen in the various art gallery and exhibition, bank and money changer, health care services, hotel/accommodation, legal offices, school and education, supermarket, minimarket, shop, phone shop, Restaurant / Cafe / Food Court, Spa, Salon, Studio, other services, non-commercial signs, traffic signs and street names, temple, furniture, stone carving and laundry.

The top-down signs found in school and education, traffic signs and street names and temple. There was found fifteen (15) outdoor signs of school and education LL classification, 53 outdoor signs of traffic signs and street names and fourteen (14) outdoor

signs of temples. Meanwhile, the rest of the signs are considered as the bottom-up classification. The Supermarket, minimarket, shop and phone shop is the dominant LL classification found in this village. There are eighty-five (85) outdoor signs found for this classification. The least LL classification found is the stone carving signs. There was found only five (5) outdoor signs of this classification.

The type of language use found in Batu Bulan are Balinese, Indonesian, English, Combination (English, Indonesia, Balinese and others) and also Universal symbols (traffic signs). The dominant language use in Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village is Indonesian. This presents the implementation of President Regulation number 63/2019. The regulation mandates the use of the Indonesian language that should be used dominantly in various aspects of written and verbal communication. The following usage applied is English, and then followed by Balinese, Combination languages and also universal symbols (traffic signs). The use of English found as the second language use in the linguistic landscape of Batu Bulan shows that some signs are dedicated for foreigners.

CONCLUSION

The LL dynamics can be seen in the various art gallery and exhibition, bank and money changer, health care services, hotel/accommodation, legal offices, school and education, supermarket, minimarket, shop, phone shop, Restaurant / Cafe / Food Court, Spa, Salon, Studio, other services, non-commercial signs, traffic signs and street names, temple, furniture, stone carving and laundry.

The top-down signs found in school and education, traffic signs and street names and temple. There was found fifteen (15) outdoor signs of school and education LL classification, 53 outdoor signs of traffic signs and street names and fourteen (14) outdoor signs of temples. Meanwhile, the rest of the signs are considered as the bottom-up classification. The Supermarket, minimarket, shop and phone shop is the dominant LL classification found in this village. There are eighty-five (85) outdoor signs found for this classification. The least LL classification found is the stone carving signs. There was found only five (5) outdoor signs of this classification.

The type of language use found in Batu Bulan are Balinese, Indonesian, English, Combination (English, Indonesia, Balinese and others) and also Universal symbols (traffic signs). The dominant language use in Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village is Indonesian. The following usage applied is English, and then followed by Balinese, Combination languages and also universal symbols (traffic signs). The use of English found as the second language use in the linguistic landscape of Batu Bulan shows that some signs are dedicated for foreigners.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to extend our gratitude to Udayana University through the Institute of Research and Community Service for giving opportunity and support our research. We also would like to extend our gratitude to English Department students, Desak Intan and Desak Tia who have assisted us with data collection.

REFERENCES

1. Baker, Mona(ed). (2000) *Routledge Encyclopedia of Translation Studies*. London: Routledge
2. Basnett, S. (002) *Translation Studies*. 3rd.ed. New York : Routledge
3. Ben-Rafael, E., Shohamy, E., Amara, M.H., Trumper-Hect, N. Linguistic Landscape as Symbolic Construction of the Public Space: The Case of Israel, *International Journal of Multilingualism*, vol 3(1), pp.7-30, <https://doi.org/10.1080/14790710608668383>
4. Catford, J.C, (1978). "A Linguistic Theory of Translation: An Essay in Applied Linguistic: Oxford University Press
5. Delabastida, D. (1993) *There's a Double Tongue: An Investigation into the translation of Shakespeare's wordplay with special reference to Hamlet*. Amsterdam: Rodopi
6. Hatim, B & Munday, J.(2004) *Translation : An Advanced Resource Book*. New York: Routledge
7. Gorter, D. Foreword: Signposts in the Linguistic Landscape in C.Helot, M.Barni, R.Janssens, and C.Bagna (eds.), *Linguistic Landscapes, Multilingualism and Social Change*, pp.9-12, Peter Lang

8. Larson, M. (1998). *Meaning-Based Translation: A Guide to Cross-Language Equivalence*. 2nd.ed. New York: University Press of America
9. Nida. E.A. (1975) *Language Structure and Translation*. Standford: Standford Univ Press
10. Denscombe, M. (1998) *The Good Research Guide*. Philadelphia: Open University Press.
11. Djajasudarma, T. Fatimah. (1993) *Metode Penelitian Linguistik: Ancangan, Metode Penelitian dan Kajian*. Bandung: PT. Eresco.
12. Ferguson, C.A (1971). *Language structure and language use*. Stanford: Stanford University Press
13. Fishman, J. A. (1972) *Sociolinguistics: A Brief Introduction*. Massachussets: Newburry House Publisher.
14. Halliday, M.A.K and Ruqaiya Hasan.(1985) *Language, Context and Text: Aspects of Language in a Social Semiotic Perspective*. Victoria: Deakin University Press
15. Hymes, D. (1964) *Language in Culture and Society*. New York: Happer and Row.
16. Hudson, R.A. (1980) *Sociolinguistics*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
17. Labov, W. *The Study of Language in Its Social Context* dalam P. P. Gigholi, ed (1972) *Language and Social Context*. Middlesex: Penguin Books Ltd.
18. Newmark, P., "Approaches to Translation", Pergamon Press, pp. 27
19. Paramarta, I.M.S. Kontestasi Bahasa Pada Tanda Luar Ruang di Daerah Pariwisata, *Sawerigading* vol 28 (1), pp.63-79, 2022
20. Puspani, I.A.M., Sosiowati, I.G.A.G., Indrawati, N.L.K.M., Purposes of Writing Signposts: The Case of the Signposts in Nusa Penida *Journal of Current Science Research and Review* vol 4 (1), pp. 59-69, 2021, <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V4-i1-10>
21. Shi, X., Analysis and Translation Strategies of Public Signs from the Perspective of Pragmatics. *Learning & Education*, vol 9 (2), pp.27, <https://ojs.piscomed.com/index.php/L-E/article/view/1390>
22. Simatupang, M.D.S., *Pengantar Teori Terjemahan*. Jakarta:Departemen Pendidikan Nasional, 2000
23. Sudaryanto. (1993) *Metode dan Aneka Teknik Analisis Bahasa*. Yogyakarta: Duta Wacana University Press
24. Sumarsono. (2007) *Sosiolinguistik*. Yogyakarta: Pustaka Pelajar

Cite this Article: Sang Ayu Isnu Maharani, Ni Luh Putu Krisnawati, Ni Ketut Widhiarcani Matradewi (2024). I Linguistic Landscape of Batu Bulan village, Gianyar. International Journal of Current Science Research and Review, 7(12), 9004-9009, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.47191/ijcsrr/V7-i12-39>